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Public Law Concept of the “Pharmaceutical Safety” : articulation problems

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Abstract. The article is devoted to comprehension of the articulation problem of the public law concept of the "pharmaceutical safety". Authors substantiated the need to distinguish pharmaceutical safety as a component of national security and security studies. It is established that the concept of "pharmaceutical safety" is not enshrined in national legislation, although some aspects of this problem are articulated at the level of by-laws. The absence of a consolidated doctrinal vision of the essence of pharmaceutical safety and its correlation with other types of national security has led to the widespread use by scientists of numerous related categories such as "pharmaceutical safety", "economic security of the pharmaceutical industry (enterprises, organizations)", "biological safety for pharmaceutical equipment", "pharmaceutical product safety", etc. It is proposed to define pharmaceutical safety as a state of maximum protection of legitimate interests of the population / patients, society, pharmaceutical and medical organizations guaranteed by the state against real and potential existential threats in the field of health care, which occur at all stages of production and circulation of medication or are determined by its inaccessibility, poor quality and / or infringement.

1 Introduction

Pharmaceutics is an industrial and technological component of pharmacy, which consists in a mass standardized production of medication. It is a goal of pharmaceutics to provide useless or even detrimental chemical compounds with pharmacological characteristics, a unique dosage form suitable for the treatment of a particular group of patients, subject to a certain route of its injection and administration schedule. Pharmaceutical industry includes the manufacture of medication and medical products used in medicine and veterinary medicine, wholesale and retail trade, specialized storage and distribution through specialized retail pharmacies, etc. Strategic groups in the pharmaceutical industry are: registered manufacturers of medication and medical products; licensed pharmaceutical wholesale companies, pharmacies, drugstores; scientific institutions developing new medication and substances; educational institutions providing training for pharmacists. The pharmaceutical industry is one of the most dynamic and profitable sectors of the economy, which is objectively conditioned by the fact that medication belongs to basic essentials, permanent increase in demand for medication in the context of the spread of chronic diseases, aging of the population, isolation of new high-tech spheres of medicine as the study of human genome needing proper pharmaceutical support. The pharmaceutical business is a special segment of the national market, traditionally characterized by increased investment attractiveness, high margin of goods, high capital intensity, high knowledge content and technological development, developed cooperation, integration with

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the field of medical services, etc. It should be noted that the public discourse also cultivates a controversial opinion about the absolute business orientation of the pharmaceutical industry on a global scale, lack of social responsibility and "predatory" commercial nature of the pharmaceutical business, its disinterest in spreading positive information about the "eradication of diseases" and the desire to "maximize profits from continuing illnesses". The pharmaceutical industry is undoubtedly particularly socially significant, of an existential nature for society and everyone as a biosocial being. Its main task is the production and timely provision of consumers with effective, safe, high quality and affordable medication. Therefore, it is subject to increased regulatory influence by public administration authorities to balance public interest and business interest, controlled by insurance medicine and civil society institutions. Permanent expansion of the range of threats in the field of health care indicates the need to initiate professional discourse on the consideration of the pharmaceutical industry in the context of ensuring national security and understanding of the essence of the public law concept of "pharmaceutical safety".

2 Results

Security is an existential imperative to ensure sustainable development of society, functioning of the state as a unique socio-legal phenomenon and unimpeded exercise of the subjective rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals. According to Article 3 (1) of the Constitution of Ukraine, human security is recognized as "of the highest social value", i.e., a person is designated as an object of national security, and human security is included in the list of unconditional public goods protected by the state. There is no unified legal definition of the generic category "security" in national legislation. Instead, in a number of by-laws, depending on the subject of legal regulation, the concept of "security" is rather eclectically interpreted as "the absence of unacceptable risk associated with the possibility of causing any harm to the life, health and property of citizens, as well as to the environment", "no risk of harm and / or damage", "a state where the risk of harm or injury is limited to an acceptable level", "a set of measures, as well as human and material resources that are designed to protect civil aviation from acts of unlawful interference and other unlawful encroachment", and even as "preventing the use of explosive material that contravenes law and threatens public order". In the absence of a legally mandated definition "security" a doctrinal interpretation of security as "a state of stability and regular functioning of a complex social system under the influence of external or internal factors" becomes essential or "a state of protection of the vital interests of the subject from the destructive influence of internal and / or external threats". The basic principles of security are defined as: observance and protection of human and citizen's rights and freedoms; inadmissibility of ensuring the safety of one person by restricting the right to the personal safety of others; systematic and comprehensive implementation of security measures; interaction of public administration authorities with civil society institutions to ensure comprehensive security.

Modern national security doctrine is based on the recognition of the core nature of the legal category of "national security". According to Clause 1, Part 1, Article 9 of the Law of Ukraine "On National Security of Ukraine", the concept of "national security of Ukraine" is defined as the protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity, democratic constitutional order and other national interests of Ukraine against real and potential threats. National security involves the implementation of a number of integrated social and legal imperatives. Therefore, national security, military security, political security, economic security, scientific and technological security, environmental security, information security, demographic security, humanitarian security, etc. are integral components of national security. The list of national security types is not exhaustive, as the range of real and potential threats to the national interests of Ukraine is constantly expanding, which in accordance with Clause 10, Part 1, Article 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On National Security of Ukraine" is defined as "vital interests of the individual, society and state, realization of which ensures the state sovereignty of Ukraine, its progressive democratic development, as well as safe living conditions and well-being of its citizens".

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The need to distinguish pharmaceutical safety as an important factor in ensuring stability, a component of national security and a separate section of security studies due to the existence of a number of significant risks and challenges, primarily the dependence of the domestic pharmaceutical industry on the import of pharmaceutical substances, a long cycle of medication development, the uncontrolled growth of private drugstore chains, reduction of medication sales through state and municipal pharmacy organizations, use of aggressive market technologies for drug promotion, presence in the pharmaceutical market of falsified, substandard and counterfeit drugs, dependence of the need for medication on emergencies / extreme situations (epidemics, pandemics, natural disasters, technogenic accidents, etc.), the need to ensure the accessibility of medication to the general public, etc. Naturally, pharmaceuticals, as a part of health care system, is of strategic importance for the realization of national interests related to research, development, mass production, study of demand and distribution of medication, mainly intended for the prevention, alleviation and treatment of diseases. Indestructible pharmaceutical truth consists in the recognition of medication as safe, provided that their technology of production, proper storage and timely use are adhered to (under all other conditions, the medical product is considered unsafe for consumers). The stabilizing factors of the pharmaceutical industry include: pharmaceutical personnel (basic and continuing pharmaceutical education, accreditation, loyalty and responsibility of staff); distribution of pharmaceutical goods (acceptance, storage, return, realization, information and consultation, accounting, quality control); premises (technical equipment, zoning, sanitary condition); pricing. Instead, the main destabilizing elements of the pharmaceutical sector are: mistakes made by pharmacists and chemists by dispensing medication; violation of the rules of taking medication; distortion of information during dispensing of medication; sale of medication via the Internet; violation of the rules of storage of medication; untimely withdrawal of substandard goods from the sale; violation of the rules of destruction of medication; lack of analysis of mistakes in the activity of specialists; lack of system for monitoring the quality and effectiveness of medication; low level of competence of specialists; admission to pharmaceutical activity of persons without specialized education, etc. That is, compliance with safety standards is provisioned at all stages of the production, distribution and use of medication.

There is no legal definition of the term "pharmaceutical safety" in the national legislation of Ukraine. Instead, some aspects of the problem are articulated at the level of the by-laws of the relevant public administration entities. Thus, according to the order of the Ministry of Healthcare of Ukraine № 460 dated 23.07.2015, the term "safety of a medical product" is interpreted as "a characteristic of a medical product based on a comparative assessment of the benefits of its use and the potential harm that cannot be inflicted on a patient by the use of this medical product". It should be noted that according to Clause 1, Part 1, Article 2 of the Law of Ukraine "On Medication" the term "medical product" is legally defined as "any substance or combination of substances (one or more active pharmaceutical ingredients and excipients) which has qualities and intended for the treatment or prevention of human diseases, or any substance or combination of substances (one or more active pharmaceutical ingredients and excipients) that may be intended to prevent pregnancy, renewal, correction or alteration of physiological functions of an individual by carrying out a pharmacological, immunological or metabolic action or in order to establish a medical diagnosis". Medication safety is a multidisciplinary phenomenon that encompasses drug monitoring and pharmacological supervision. It must be continuously ensured at the stages of their development and industrial production, preclinical and clinical research, registration and monitoring throughout the life cycle of each specific medical product.

In domestic science the discourse on the essence of the complex public law concept of "pharmaceutical safety" continues. The analysis of publications on pharmaceutical safety issues shows terminological variability and eclecticism. The specificity of methodological approaches led to the articulation of the following related categories:

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- "economic security of the pharmaceutical industry" as a state of the pharmaceutical industry, which ensures the effective implementation of its economic and social functions, as well as its "development through the detection, prevention and elimination of threats";

- "pharmaceutical organization / enterprise security" as an integral indicator of ensuring financial, personnel, technological, legal and information security of the pharmaceutical organization / enterprise;

- "pharmaceutical safety" as a reasonable state of belief that pharmaceutical products are safe to use under normal conditions, are not harmful, pose no threats to health and do not influence the environment. The safety of pharmaceutical products is formed in the system "person - product - environment". The dualistic nature of the safety of pharmaceutical products leads to the separation of the safety of medication consumption and the environmental safety of pharmaceutical products. It is emphasized that the safety of medication consumption is ensured in the absence of: traumatic effects on the body (mechanical, electrical, thermal, chemical); discharge of substances harmful to the body (toxic / poisonous, allergic, carcinogenic, mutational, etc.); dangerous physical effects (radiation, sound / noise, light, etc.); specific side effects and contraindications related to the specific qualities of an addiction to a particular medication (drug addiction, toxicomania); drug withdrawal syndrome. Environmental safety of pharmaceutical products is characterized by the degree of environmental impact of the medical product (the level of environmental pollution caused by pharmaceutical production waste).

Instead, the term pharmaceutical safety is alternatively interpreted in the following meanings:

- as a safety of medical products at the stages of development, industrial production, preclinical and clinical trials, official registration, transportation, storage, distribution, monitoring of medical use and disposal safety;

- as reducing the dependence on medicines imports as a result of the accelerated development of the national pharmaceutical industry (the World Health Organization states that pharmaceutical safety can be ensured when the proportion of domestic pharmaceuticals in the domestic market reaches at least 70%);

- as a combat with falsified, substandard and counterfeit medicines;

- as assurance that medication is consistent with clinical practice standards;

- as a preservation of the quality of medication at the stage of production, transportation, storage and distribution.

It is quite common to identify the concepts of "pharmaceutical safety" and "medication safety" based on the absolutization of the criteria of the production safety and the safety of the pharmacological action of medication.

A comprehensive analysis of the state of the pharmaceutical safety discourse gives grounds to argue for the fundamental nature of distinguishing pharmaceutical safety as a type of national security of two interconnected safety macrospheres, namely: patient safety in the medication / pharmaceutical products consumption system (narrowly interpreted as "medication safety" and broadly defined as "pharmaceutical product safety"); safety of business entities engaged in the development, industrial production, transportation, storage and distribution of medical products ("safety of pharmaceutical organizations / enterprises"). On the other hand, it is essential for understanding the socio-legal nature of pharmaceutical safety that it is perceived as an integral indicator of medication safety and a marker of the effectiveness of identifying and eliminating threats at the stages of "gross value creation, consumption, and disposal of medical products".

It is axiomatic that pharmaceutical safety shall guarantee the interests of the patient, society and the pharmaceutical market operators. Therefore, we consider it expedient to define pharmaceutical safety in the broadest sense as the state of maximum protection of legitimate interests of the population / patients, society, pharmaceutical and medical organizations guaranteed by the state against real and potential existential threats in the field of healthcare, which arise by development, industrial production, preclinical and clinical trials, state registration, transportation, storage, distribution, medical use and

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disposal of medical products, as well as determined by availability, poor quality and falsification / counterfeiting of medical products.

For the moment, urgent need to build a public system on the human-centered grounds to ensure pharmaceutical security is escalated. The existential imperatives of public administration in the field of pharmaceutical safety are to minimize import dependency and increase the level of competitiveness of domestic companies in the global pharmaceutical market, systematic introduction of innovative pharmaceutical products by domestic pharmaceutical enterprises, creation of appropriate non-discriminatory conditions for the activities of pharmaceutical operators and consumers, stable provision of the population with a wide range of quality and affordable medication, formation of the necessary stock of medication in case of emergency and / or crisis situations, strict adherence to current international environmental safety standards in development, industrial production, transportation, storage, distribution, medical use and utilization of medical products, etc.

3 Conclusion

To summarize, a nation's health indicator is an objective comprehensive indicator of a country's socio-economic development, a marker of the human-centricity of public administration, an imperative to ensure the sustainable development of society and maximize the self-fulfillment of each person. The pharmaceutical industry as a strategic unit of the national economic complex is of existential importance. Pharmaceutical safety as an integral component of national security should be defined as the state of maximum protection of legitimate interests of the population / patients, society, pharmaceutical and medical organizations guaranteed by the state against real and potential existential threats in the field of healthcare, which arise from development, industrial production, preclinical and clinical trials, official registration, transportation, storage, distribution, medical use and disposal of medical products, as well as inaccessibility, poor quality and counterfeiting / falsification of medication.

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